

Sixty-year impact of manure and NPK on soil aggregate stability

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ABSTRACT

Understanding how long-term land use affects soil quality and resistance to degradation is essential for identifying sustainable management practices in different soil types. This study's aim was to evaluate how different fertilization approaches influence soil aggregate stability (SAS) and some associated soil properties. The experiment was established in 1955 at three sites with different soil types (Chernozem on loess, Phaeozem on loess, and Cambisol on gneiss) and diverse climatic conditions. Three fertilization scenarios were selected for the study conducted during 2014–2021: i) farmyard manure (40 t ha⁻¹) once every 4 years; ii) NPK mineral fertilizer every year plus farmyard manure once every 4 years, and iii) no fertilizer (control).

Farmyard manure positively affected stability of the Cambisol soil aggregates in both cases of fertilization (i and ii). On the other hand, manure had negligible impact upon SAS of the other two soils. In addition, significantly lower SAS values were measured for soils fertilized also by the mineral fertilizer (ii) than for the other scenarios (i and iii). Manure treatment and combined fertilization showed a significant increase in hot water extractable carbon and total carbon content at all sites compared to the unfertilized treatments. A positive relationship between SAS and total organic carbon was confirmed, however, only for the Cambisol spring samples. In some years, composition of organic matter or content of glomalin was also investigated to reveal their effects on SAS. A positive impact of hydrophobicity on SAS was proven for the Phaeozem and Chernozem, but not for the Cambisol. An unexpected negative effect was observed for glomalin. For both spring and summer sampling events, the SAS values were strongly and negatively correlated with the field (sampling) soil water content, which partly masked effects of other soil properties on SAS. These results underscore the importance of complex long-term studies for understanding mutual interactions affecting the stability of soil aggregates in individual soil types and different climatic conditions.

1. Introduction

Structure is one of soil's most important properties. It directly or indirectly affects all processes in soil. Soil structure is influenced by physical, chemical, and biological interactions in soil (Regelink et al., 2015). Understanding the processes of soil aggregates formation and stabilization is essential for determining sustainable soil management (Bronick and Lal, 2005). Because arable land is degraded as a result of agricultural practices (Pagliari et al., 2004; Kodešová et al., 2008; Kodešová et al., 2009; Kodešová et al., 2011), the study of how different land management methods influence soil structure is a very important and current topic.

Research on the interaction between agricultural activities and soil

structure is mainly concerned with the effect of soil processing and plant cultivation methods, the effect of mineral and organic fertilizer application, the effect of soil organisms, and the interaction of these factors with habitat conditions. The stability of soil aggregates under conventional tillage, minimum tillage, and no-till systems has been studied. For example, Alvaro-Fuentes et al. (2008) and Kasper et al. (2009) point to a positive effect on soil aggregation of decreasing tillage intensity. Papadopoulos et al. (2014) showed a positive effect of organic farming on organic matter content, soil aggregate stability (SAS), and porosity compared to conventional farming.

The consensus of the scientific community as to the effect of fertilization is ambiguous, especially regarding mineral fertilizers. Naveed et al. (2014) stated, for example, that fertilization with organic and

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inorganic fertilizers has a strong positive effect on soil structure, organism activity, and the amount of organic carbon. Similarly, Zhang et al. (2021) showed that both mineral and organic (pig manure) fertilization or their combination improved soil aggregation. Anthonio et al. (2022) documented just a slight influence of mineral fertilizer and significant impact of pig manure. Also, Chen et al. (2021) showed that mineral fertilizers increased aggregate stability only slightly, but in combination with organic material (soybean litter) they substantially increased stability of soil aggregates. Zhou et al. (2013) concluded that organic fertilizers improve soil aggregation while inorganic fertilizers are inefficient in doing so. No effect of mineral fertilizer and positive effect of manure or combined application of mineral fertilizer and manure on soil aggregates was also observed by, among others, Abdalla et al. (2023), Gautam et al. (2022), and Mi et al. (2018). Marinari et al. (2000) observed that while addition of organic fertilizers improved the physical and biological properties of soil, mineral fertilizer caused an increase in soil porosity and enzymatic activity. The effect of different fertilization treatments (no fertilization, NPK, and NPK + manure) on hydraulic properties, bulk density, porosity, soil organic matter (SOM), and soil water content was studied by Zhang et al. (2006), who concluded that the application of manure and mineral fertilizers positively affected soil's physical properties.

Farmyard manure fertilization is widely recognized as a method of improving soil structure and fertility through the addition of organic matter and nutrients (Guo et al., 2019). Nevertheless, the development of optimal application rates for manure and inorganic fertilizers, as well as their impacts on soils quality and the overall environment, remain under investigation. These findings and proposed suitable approaches are needed to avoid long-term negative effects on the environment. For example, Ozlu et al. (2022) pointed to increase in electrical conductivity and emissions of greenhouse gas. Although cow manure is rich in nutrients, its use has limitations, particularly in arid and semi-arid areas, due to its salinity (Karami et al., 2012).

The main factors affecting aggregate stability are organic matter, clay, and oxides of Fe, Mn, Al, and other metals (e.g., Jakšík et al., 2015; Kodešová et al., 2009; Pavlů et al., 2021; Pavlů et al., 2022; Rasmussen et al., 2018; Zádorová et al., 2011). The most important of these is organic matter, and therefore it is widely assumed that addition of organic fertilizers such as manure or various organic mulches should enhance stability of soils aggregates. However, the effect of the added material strongly depends on its decomposition rate and on the final composition of the SOM. In general, hydrophobic components stabilize the structure (Thai et al., 2022) and also protect aggregates against destruction thanks to their water repellency (Fér et al., 2016). Water repellency of an aggregate's surface slows the penetration of water into the aggregate and thereby prevents its destruction by protecting the compressed air enclosed inside the aggregate. Changes of SOM and its labile and stable components can be distinguished using Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, which is well suited for evaluating the effects of soil management (Calderón et al., 2013; Pavlů et al., 2023; Thai et al., 2021) and quality of the applied organic enrichments (Fér et al., 2024).

The relationship between soil structure and microbial activity contributes to a mutually supporting cycle, as a good soil structure contributes to high microbial activity and vice versa (Cui and Holden, 2015). Roots, soil fungi, and bacteria cement aggregates directly or produce viscous substances that promote aggregation (Bronick and Lal, 2005). Increased nutrient supply affects not only plant communities but also microbial communities, and long-term applications of mineral N can alter soil microbial composition (Geisseler and Scow, 2014).

Zhang et al. (2015) pointed out that one of the main factors stabilizing soil aggregates is the glycoprotein glomalin (Wright and Upadhyaya, 1998). Glomalin is secreted into the soil by the mycelia of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi and acts as a sealer in the soil. The issue of glomalin in relation to, for example, soil carbon stock (Fokom et al., 2012), heavy metal fixation (Wu et al., 2014), and stability of soil

aggregates (Gispert et al., 2013) is a much-debated topic. Some studies address the possibility of using glomalin values in determining changes in soil properties during degradation processes (Šarapatka et al., 2019). The glomalin content in soil is influenced by type of land use, tillage method (Gałązka et al., 2017; García-Orenes et al., 2012), and fertilization (Turgay et al., 2015).

Studies dealing with the assessment of various management types on soil structure stability usually provide results from a single sampling campaign. Jirků et al. (2013), however, who studied topsoil properties of three soil types under conventional tillage during a 4-year period, showed that stability of soil aggregates varies significantly during the year (depending on factors such as soil consolidation, soil swelling and shrinking, and roots activity) and even differs considerably between years (depending on overall climatic conditions). They also documented soil aggregate stability (SAS) to be negatively correlated with field (sampling) water content.

This study aims to clarify some of the aforementioned aspects related to the impact of different fertilization methods (no fertilizers, manure, and both NPK and manure) on the stability of soil aggregates. Because the effects of mineral and organic fertilizers may differ in various soils, three different soils and sets of climate conditions were considered. In the selected localities, different fertilization methods have been applied since 1955. Thus, our study examined not the immediate effect of a change in land management on soil properties but rather the long-term effect after a semi-equilibrium of soil processes has been achieved. Additionally, because stability of soil aggregates (depending on climatic conditions and crop) can vary considerably from year to year and results obtained in one year can be misleading, the experiment was carried out over a period of 8 years (2014–2021) when different crops were grown every year. The aim was to test the widely assumed hypothesis that manure should considerably improve soil structure in all cases regardless of the application of inorganic fertilizer that can negatively affect soil structure. Along with SAS, other properties that should be affected by different treatments (such as content and composition of organic matter, content of glomalin, and some hydro-physical parameters) were also investigated. While some of those properties were analyzed for each sampling campaign, the measurement of other parameters was not consistent, because it corresponded to current requirements of the specific projects associated with long-term experiments carried out at all three locations. Nevertheless, another aim of this study was to provide synthesis of all available data, meaning to find relationships among all available soil characteristics and to discover the either positive or negative effects of soil properties on the stability of soil aggregates. Finally, benefits related to crop yield due to fertilizers application are discussed with respect to the effect of fertilizers on soil-structure quality.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Description of the long-term field experiment

This study was carried out within long-term field experiments established in the autumn of 1955 on experimental plots of the Crop Research Institute in Čáslav near Kutná Hora, Lukavec near Pacov, and Ivanovice na Hané (all in the Czech Republic). The methodology of these long-term experiments was described in detail by Kunzová and Hejman (2009). The experiment is in all cases conducted on 4 strips with a uniform crop rotation system: winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), silage maize (*Zea mays* L.), spring barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.), winter rape (*Brassica napus* L.), winter wheat (*T. aestivum*), potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.), spring barley (*H. vulgare*) with red clover underseeding, and red clover (*Trifolium pratense* L.). Each strip is divided into 12 plots (8 × 8 m) and on each of these a different type of fertilizer is applied. The same 12 variants of fertilization (i.e., fertilization system and rates) are used on all 4 strips. However, their arrangement within each strip is different. Mineral nitrogen was applied as lime ammonium nitrate, phosphorus as superphosphate, potassium as potassium salt, and

magnesium as Kieserite. Three variants with different fertilization regimes were selected for this study: control (no fertilization), manure (40 t ha⁻¹ applied once every 4 years before growing corn and potato), and full fertilization (manure applied once every 4 years plus NPK mineral fertilization in average doses of N 66 kg ha⁻¹, P 40 kg ha⁻¹, and K 87 kg ha⁻¹ applied every year). The source of manure was farmyard cattle manure from local farmers, always applied in the autumn and incorporated into the soil within 24 h. Properties of the manure from different sources varied over time. For example, dry mass varied between 20 % and 40 %, pH_{H2O} was in the range 8.3–9.0, and contents of NPK as percent of dry mass were 1.2–3.3 % for N, 0.30–0.89 % for P, and 1.5–4.9 % for K. Conventional tillage to the depth of 20 cm was used during the entire experiment.

2.2. Characteristics of sites

The locations are characterized by different soil and climatic conditions. Detailed description of the sites has been published by Hlisenkóvský et al. (2020) and Stehlík et al. (2019). Čáslav (GPS: N 49°85', E 15°40') is located at altitude 263 m a.s.l., the average total annual precipitation is 572 mm, and the average annual temperature is 9.3 °C (Čáslav Meteorological Station). The soil type is a Greyic Phaeozem developed on loess (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022), and soil texture is silty loam (20.5 % clay, 62.8 % silt, and 16.7 % sand). Ivanovice na Hané (GPS: N 49°19', E 17°05') is at altitude 225 m a.s.l., the average total annual precipitation is 548 mm, and the average annual temperature is 9.2 °C (Ivanovice Meteorological Station). The soil type is a Haplic Chernozem developed on loess (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022), and soil texture is silty loam (24.0 % clay, 62.9 % silt, and 13.2 % sand). Lukavec (GPS: N 49°34', E 14°59') is at altitude 620 m a.s.l., the average total annual precipitation is 683 mm, and the average annual temperatures is 7.7 °C (Lukavec Meteorological Station). The soil type is a Eutric Cambisol developed on gneiss (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022), and soil texture is sandy loam (8.5 % clay, 32.2 % silt, and 59.3 % sand).

2.3. Soil sampling and analyses

The study was performed during the 8-year period 2014–2021. The mean monthly temperatures and precipitation totals are shown in Fig. S1. Crops grown in this period and their yields during 2014–2020 are shown in Fig. S2. Oat (*Avena sativa* L.) with red clover underseeding was grown instead of spring barley in 2020. Yield for clover grown in 2021 was not assessed. Soil samples were usually collected in spring (after sowing or before the growing season in the case of winter crops) and summer (after harvest). Disturbed samples of topsoil (0–20 cm) were taken in each experimental plot and stored in plastic boxes to avoid soil structure destruction during transportation. In addition, three 100 cm³ undisturbed soil samples were collected from a depth of 5–10 cm during the summer sampling events to study selected hydro-physical properties of well-consolidated soil structure.

Gravimetric soil water content (w_{field}), which is the ratio of water mass per mass of dry soil expressed in percentage, was evaluated on the fresh soil samples collected in spring. Volumetric soil water content (θ_{field}), which is the ratio of water volume per volume of undisturbed soil sample expressed in percentage, was evaluated on the fresh soil samples collected in summer. Due to the soil disturbance in spring, it would make no sense to collect and analyze samples for water content at this time.

All disturbed soil samples were air dried and divided into two parts. From the first of these, aggregates between 1 and 2 mm in size were extracted using 1 and 2 mm sieves. Their stability was then investigated by the wet sieving method (Kandeler, 1996) using HERZOG laboratory equipment (Adolf Herzog GmbH, Vienna, Austria). Four grams of aggregates were placed into a 0.25 mm sieve (in 3 replicates) and sieved for 5 min in distilled water. Stable aggregates were then destroyed by sieving in a solution of Na₄P₂O₇·10H₂O, leaving only the sand fraction in the sieve. Soil aggregates stability (SAS) was calculated as follows:

$$\%SAS = \frac{(M2 - M3)}{W - (M3 - M1)} * 100, \quad (1)$$

where M1 is the weight of the bowl (g), M2 is the weight of the bowl with stable aggregates and sand (g), M3 is the weight of the bowl with sand remaining in the sieve after sieving in solution of Na₄P₂O₇·10H₂O (g), W is the initial sample weight, and 100 is the conversion factor.

Furthermore, this fraction of soil aggregates sampled in spring 2018 and 2019 was also used to determine total and easily extractable glomalin, which was extracted by autoclaving in neutral or alkaline sodium citrate solution (Wright and Upadhyaya, 1996) and subsequently quantified using a nonspecific colorimetric assay according to Bradford (1976) on a spectrophotometer (S-20, BOECO, Hamburg, Germany).

From the second part of the bulk sample, fine soil was extracted using a 2 mm sieve. This material was next used to measure hot water extractable carbon (C_{hwi}) according to Körschens et al. (1990), total organic carbon (C_{tot}) and total organic nitrogen (N_{tot}) using a Vario MAX CNS/CN analyzer (Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Hanau, Germany), and the active soil reaction (pH_{H2O}) (ISO 10390, 2005).

Furthermore, soil organic matter (SOM) components were measured on samples taken in springs of 2018, 2019, 2020, and 2021 using FTIR spectroscopy. FTIR spectra were measured using a Thermo Nicolet Avatar 320 FTIR spectrometer (Nicolet, Madison, WI, USA) in a homogeneous mixture of bulk soil and FTIR-grade potassium bromide solution (Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany). Next, the following functional groups as characterized by particular absorption bands were analyzed: hydrophobic (aliphatic) C–H groups (3000–2800 cm⁻¹), hydrophilic C=O groups (1740–1600 cm⁻¹), and aromatic C=C groups (1660–1580 cm⁻¹) (Demyan et al., 2012; Mayerová et al., 2023). It should be noted that aromatic rings in this range, generally assumed to indicate hydrophobic groups, show hydrophilic properties if they are conjugated with C=O groups (Ellerbrock et al., 2005; Leue et al., 2010). The hydrophobicity index (HI) and decomposition index (DI) were calculated as follows (Ellerbrock et al., 2005; Margenot et al., 2015; Mayerová et al., 2023):

$$HI = \frac{A}{B} * 100, \quad (2)$$

$$DI = \frac{AR}{AL} * 100, \quad (3)$$

where A and B are the intensity of FTIR spectra for hydrophobic and hydrophilic functional groups, respectively, and AR and AL are the intensity of FTIR spectra for aromatic and aliphatic functional groups, respectively. Both analyses of FTIR spectra and glomalin content were performed only for spring samples in order to avoid the possible impact of fresh organic matter at the end of the vegetation season.

On the other hand, the hydro-physical properties (saturated volumetric soil water content [θ_s], 30-min soil water content [θ_{30}], maximum capillary water capacity [θ_{MCK}], and water retention capacity [θ_{RVK}]) were determined on the undisturbed 100 cm³ soil samples taken during the summer sampling events according to Spasić et al. (2023). Briefly, undisturbed soil samples were first saturated on a saturation pan. After their full saturation, they were weighed (to determine θ_s) and placed onto four times folded filter paper. After 30 min, they were weighed (to determine θ_{30}) and placed again onto the four times folded filter paper for another 90 min. After weighing (to determine θ_{MCK}), they were again placed onto the four times folded filter paper for another 22 h (to determine θ_{RVK}). Next, the samples were dried at 105 °C. Corresponding volumetric water contents were calculated as follows:

$$\theta_i = \frac{m_{wi} - m_d}{\rho_d V}, \quad (4)$$

where θ_i is a particular volumetric soil water content, m_{wi} and m_d are masses of wet and dry soil samples (g), respectively, ρ_d is the water

density (1 g cm^{-3} for $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), and V is the volume of soil sample (cm^3). This method has long been used in the Czech Republic instead of more sophisticated methods, such as the pressure plate apparatus, when it is necessary to analyze a large amount of soil samples (Almaz et al., 2023; Spasić et al., 2023). Standard methods (Dane and Topp, 2002) were applied to obtain specific density (ρ_s), bulk density (ρ_d), and porosity (P).

2.4. Statistical analyses

STATISTICA 14.0.0.15 software (TIBCO Software Inc., USA) was used for statistical data evaluation. Basic statistical values were calculated (i.e., means and standard deviations). The basic relationships among the corresponding soil properties (variables available either for spring or summer sampling events) were assessed using correlation analysis (Pearson correlation coefficient [r]). While analyses of aggregate stability were made in all sampling campaigns except those for spring 2016 and 2017, the measurement of other parameters was not consistent (Tables 1 and 2). Correlation analyses always included all data (sampling years) available for each pair of correlated values. Statistical significance was assessed by p -values at significance levels 0.05, 0.01, and 0.001. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to compare the effect of fertilization treatments on SAS, glomalin content, and yield. This was followed by post hoc analysis using Tukey's HSD test at significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ to determine homogeneous groups. Multifactorial analysis of variance was used to determine the interaction of treatment and year effects on SAS and other soil properties. Then, post

hoc tests (Scheffé tests) at the 0.05 significance level were performed for multiple comparison. Analyses always included all data (years of sampling) available for a given variable. Furthermore, multiple linear regression was used to express the relationships between the stability of soil aggregates and other soil properties. Finally, principal component analyses (PCAs) were performed using STATGRAPHICS Centurion XV Version 15.2.06 to assess general differences and trends between the treatments.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Soil organic matter

The hot water extractable carbon (C_{hwl}) and total organic carbon (C_{tot}) contents varied in time depending on the site conditions. Manure fertilization and combined fertilization (NPK + manure) significantly increased the C_{hwl} and C_{tot} contents at all sites compared to the unfertilized treatments (Tables 1 and 2). That is consistent with the findings of Abdalla et al. (2022) and Khan et al. (2022), who studied the effect of joint application of organic and inorganic fertilizers on soil organic carbon. The positive effect of organic fertilization is associated with increased soil organic carbon content and a change in the distribution of SOM components in favor of the hydrophobic component (Table 1). However, correlations between the C_{hwl} and the HI values ($R = 0.372$, 0.297 , and 0.276 , for the Phaeozem in Čáslav, Chernozem in Ivanovice, and Cambisol in Lukavec, respectively; Tables S2, S4 and S6) were not as

Table 1

Analyses of soil aggregate stability, spring samplings. Different letters indicate significant differences between means (\pm standard errors) at $\alpha = 0.05$ for given variables (Scheffé test, multifactorial ANOVA). SAS – soil aggregate stability (%), DI – decomposition index, HI – hydrophobicity index, C_{hwl} – hot water extractable carbon (mg g^{-1}), C_{tot} – total organic carbon (%), N_{tot} – total organic nitrogen (%), TG – total glomalin (mg g^{-1}), EEG – easily extracted glomalin (mg g^{-1}), w_{field} – field gravimetric soil water content (%). Hydrophobic aliphatic, aromatic, and hydrophilic refer to soil organic matter components.

season	properties	treatment	Čáslav	Ivanovice	Lukavec	sampling	
spring	SAS	manure	28.86 \pm 1.71 a	29.06 \pm 1.57 a	51.88 \pm 0.95 a	2014, 2015, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021	
		NPK + manure	24.52 \pm 1.71 b	25.55 \pm 1.59 b	50.58 \pm 1.26 a		
		control	29.45 \pm 1.73 a	29.20 \pm 1.82 a	46.19 \pm 1.15 b		
	aliphatic	manure	1.21 \pm 0.13 a	1.24 \pm 0.07 a	1.88 \pm 0.08 a		2018, 2019, 2020, 2021
		NPK + manure	1.27 \pm 0.11 a	1.54 \pm 0.11 b	2.00 \pm 0.08 a		
		control	0.93 \pm 0.10 b	1.32 \pm 0.13 ab	1.76 \pm 0.11 a		
	aromatic	manure	3.35 \pm 0.11 a	3.34 \pm 0.90 a	1.77 \pm 0.12 a	2018, 2019, 2020, 2021	
		NPK + manure	3.31 \pm 0.12 a	3.25 \pm 0.11 a	1.91 \pm 0.09 a		
		control	3.62 \pm 0.13 b	3.38 \pm 0.11 a	1.78 \pm 0.11 a		
	hydrophilic	manure	5.84 \pm 0.27 a	6.45 \pm 0.23 a	6.55 \pm 0.22 a		2018, 2019, 2020, 2021
		NPK + manure	5.68 \pm 0.28 a	6.27 \pm 0.19 a	6.31 \pm 0.27 a		
		control	5.90 \pm 0.25 a	6.43 \pm 0.23 a	6.16 \pm 0.27 a		
	DI	manure	3.45 \pm 0.45 a	2.91 \pm 0.24 a	0.99 \pm 0.09 a	2014, 2015, 2016, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021	
		NPK + manure	3.00 \pm 0.32 a	2.46 \pm 0.38 a	0.98 \pm 0.06 a		
		control	4.71 \pm 0.51 b	3.08 \pm 0.38 a	1.11 \pm 0.12 a		
	HI	manure	0.22 \pm 0.03 ab	0.20 \pm 0.02 a	0.29 \pm 0.02 a		2014, 2018, 2020, 2021
		NPK + manure	0.24 \pm 0.03 a	0.25 \pm 0.02 b	0.33 \pm 0.02 a		
		control	0.17 \pm 0.03 b	0.22 \pm 0.03 ab	0.30 \pm 0.03 a		
	C_{hwl}	manure	0.40 \pm 0.01 a	0.49 \pm 0.01 a	0.49 \pm 0.01 a	2014, 2015, 2016, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021	
		NPK + manure	0.42 \pm 0.01 a	0.47 \pm 0.02 a	0.48 \pm 0.02 a		
		control	0.33 \pm 0.01 b	0.40 \pm 0.01 b	0.37 \pm 0.01 b		
C_{tot}	manure	1.49 \pm 0.03 a	2.15 \pm 0.03 a	1.59 \pm 0.02 a	2014, 2018, 2020, 2021		
	NPK + manure	1.59 \pm 0.02 b	2.19 \pm 0.03 a	1.56 \pm 0.04 a			
	control	1.35 \pm 0.02 c	1.92 \pm 0.03 b	1.33 \pm 0.02 b			
N_{tot}	manure	0.14 \pm 0.00 a	0.19 \pm 0.00 a	0.15 \pm 0.00 a		2018, 2019	
	NPK + manure	0.15 \pm 0.00 b	0.19 \pm 0.00 a	0.15 \pm 0.00 a			
	control	0.13 \pm 0.00 b	0.17 \pm 0.00 a	0.13 \pm 0.00 b			
TG	manure	2.13 \pm 0.12 a	2.75 \pm 0.17 a	1.52 \pm 0.17 ab	2015, 2018, 2020, 2021		
	NPK + manure	2.85 \pm 0.30 b	3.27 \pm 0.25 ab	1.72 \pm 0.24 a			
	control	2.04 \pm 0.15 a	3.33 \pm 0.38 b	1.24 \pm 0.14 b			
EEG	manure	0.44 \pm 0.04 a	0.61 \pm 0.07 a	0.56 \pm 0.08 a		2018, 2019	
	NPK + manure	0.47 \pm 0.04 a	0.55 \pm 0.06 a	0.58 \pm 0.08 a			
	control	0.40 \pm 0.03 a	0.49 \pm 0.03 a	0.47 \pm 0.06 b			
$\text{pH}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	manure	7.34 \pm 0.10 a	7.45 \pm 0.11 ab	6.65 \pm 0.06 a	2018, 2019		
	NPK + manure	7.15 \pm 0.10 b	7.33 \pm 0.09 a	6.52 \pm 0.08 b			
	control	7.41 \pm 0.08 a	7.57 \pm 0.08 b	6.61 \pm 0.06 ab			
w_{field}	manure	13.47 \pm 0.55 a	10.53 \pm 1.47 a	11.41 \pm 1.47 a		2018, 2019, 2020, 2021	
	NPK + manure	13.47 \pm 0.58 a	10.44 \pm 1.34 a	12.40 \pm 1.51 a			
	control	12.73 \pm 0.53 b	10.03 \pm 1.25 a	11.41 \pm 1.27 a			

Table 2

Analyses of soil aggregate stability, summer samplings. Different letters indicate significant differences between means (\pm standard error) at $\alpha = 0.05$ for given variables (Scheffé test, multifactorial ANOVA). SAS – soil aggregate stability (%), C_{tot} – total organic carbon (%), N_{tot} – total organic nitrogen (%), θ_{field} – field volumetric soil water content (%), θ_s – soil moisture saturated (%), θ_{30} –30-min moisture (%), θ_{MCK} – maximum capillary water capacity (%), θ_{RVK} – water retention capacity (%), ρ_d – bulk density (g cm^{-3}), P – porosity (%).

season	properties	treatment	Čáslav	Ivanovice	Lukavec	sampling
summer	SAS	manure	33.14 \pm 3.69 a	26.2 \pm 1.10 ab	52.29 \pm 2.55 a	2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021
		NPK + manure	28.81 \pm 3.59 b	23.3 \pm 0.90 a	50.65 \pm 2.65 a	
		control	33.08 \pm 3.42 a	27.9 \pm 1.01 b	47.85 \pm 2.31 b	
	C_{tot}	manure	1.28 \pm 0.01 a	1.94 \pm 0.02 a	1.73 \pm 0.03 a	
		NPK + manure	1.33 \pm 0.02 b	1.94 \pm 0.02 a	1.68 \pm 0.02 a	
		control	1.17 \pm 0.02 c	1.63 \pm 0.02 b	1.44 \pm 0.02 b	
	N_{tot}	manure	0.16 \pm 0.00 a	0.23 \pm 0.00 a	0.22 \pm 0.00 a	
		NPK + manure	0.17 \pm 0.00 b	0.23 \pm 0.00 a	0.21 \pm 0.00 a	
		control	0.15 \pm 0.00 c	0.19 \pm 0.00 b	0.19 \pm 0.00 b	
	θ_{field}	manure	24.70 \pm 1.68 a	24.42 \pm 0.82 a	25.44 \pm 1.74 a	
		NPK + manure	25.07 \pm 1.72 a	24.14 \pm 0.80 a	25.65 \pm 1.58 a	
		control	24.65 \pm 1.62 a	23.37 \pm 0.80 a	24.03 \pm 1.66 b	
	θ_s	manure	42.05 \pm 0.34 a	41.70 \pm 0.38 a	40.09 \pm 0.63 a	
		NPK + manure	41.99 \pm 0.53 a	41.79 \pm 0.33 a	39.92 \pm 0.49 a	
		control	39.57 \pm 0.51 b	41.28 \pm 0.32 a	39.38 \pm 0.44 a	
	θ_{30}	manure	38.06 \pm 0.27 a	36.66 \pm 0.39 a	36.24 \pm 0.45 a	
		NPK + manure	38.31 \pm 0.40 a	36.82 \pm 0.40 a	36.10 \pm 0.54 a	
		control	36.25 \pm 0.34 b	36.18 \pm 0.32 a	34.80 \pm 0.53 b	
	θ_{MCK}	manure	35.05 \pm 0.37 ab	33.81 \pm 0.41 a	33.43 \pm 0.57 a	
		NPK + manure	35.53 \pm 0.48 a	33.99 \pm 0.44 a	33.32 \pm 0.58 a	
		control	33.92 \pm 0.45b	33.01 \pm 0.40 b	32.17 \pm 0.53 a	
	θ_{RVK}	manure	28.80 \pm 0.58 a	28.75 \pm 0.50 a	27.56 \pm 0.62 a	
		NPK + manure	29.59 \pm 0.69 a	28.62 \pm 0.49 a	27.25 \pm 0.56 a	
		control	28.72 \pm 0.69 a	27.82 \pm 0.48 b	26.03 \pm 0.53 b	
ρ_d	manure	1.384 \pm 0.01 a	1.314 \pm 0.02 a	1.361 \pm 0.01 a		
	NPK + manure	1.383 \pm 0.01 a	1.319 \pm 0.02 a	1.354 \pm 0.01 a		
	control	1.407 \pm 0.01 a	1.339 \pm 0.02 a	1.395 \pm 0.02 a		
P	manure	46.05 \pm 0.41 a	48.08 \pm 0.58 a	47.37 \pm 0.54 a		
	NPK + manure	46.08 \pm 0.48 a	47.85 \pm 0.59 a	47.63 \pm 0.49 a		
	control	45.15 \pm 0.53 a	47.07 \pm 0.61 a	46.06 \pm 0.62 a		

strong as could be anticipated (e.g., Balík et al., 2022). Nevertheless, as in the previous study by Stehlíková et al. (2016), significant positive correlations between C_{hwl} and aliphatic (hydrophobic) components of SOM ($R = 0.406, 0.339$ and 0.417) and significant (except Lukavec) negative correlation between C_{hwl} and aromatic components of SOM ($R = -0.441, -0.402$, and -0.182) were found for Čáslav, Ivanovice, and Lukavec, respectively. The highest values of the decomposition index (DI) were always obtained for the control variants and the DI values were significantly and negatively correlated with the C_{hwl} values (i.e., $R = -0.474, -0.484$, and -0.408 for Čáslav, Ivanovice, and Lukavec, respectively). In addition, C_{tot} in Čáslav was significantly correlated with aliphatic ($R = 0.531$) and aromatic ($R = -0.389$) components, DI ($R =$

-0.552), and HI ($R = 0.392$). This shows that a lower degree of decomposition is positively associated with an increase of soil organic carbon (Margenot et al., 2015).

3.2. Glomalin

The contents of total glomalin (TG) and easily extractable glomalin (EEG) were measured in 2018 and 2019 (Fig. 1, Table S1). In general, the highest content of glomalin was found in the Chernozem in Ivanovice, followed by the Phaeozem in Čáslav and the Cambisol in Lukavec. TG content was significantly lower in 2018 than in 2019 (Fig. 1). Manure application could have been a factor contributing to increase in

Fig. 1. Effect of year on total glomalin (TG) (left) and effect of treatment on TG in 2019 (right). Letters a and b indicate scenarios belonging to the same groups (i.e., significant differences at level $\alpha = 0.05$, Tukey's HSD test). Vertical lines show 95 % confidence intervals. While all results are compared on left, results from different treatments are compared for each site on right.

the content of glomalin observed in 2019. As reported by Curaqueo et al. (2011), increased glomalin content is usually observed after the application of an organic material, especially stable manure, cattle slurry, or compost. The low TG values in 2018 could be due to higher temperatures and lower total precipitation (Fig. S1), as these could negatively affect the growth of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (Maitra et al., 2019), which produce glomalin. In order to confirm this hypothesis, we would need a longer period of observation and a focus on individual taxa of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, because, as Augé (2001) states, temporary drought can, on the contrary, stimulate spore production in some fungi. It probably is for similar reasons that a significant effect of different treatments was detected only in 2019 (Fig. 1, Table S1). In Čáslav and Lukavec, the highest TG and EEG values were found for the variant fertilized with NPK + manure, followed by manure and control. Similar trends had been observed by Balík et al. (2023), who studied the effect of different fertilizations in Luvisols. In Ivanovice, however, the highest TG values were obtained for the control followed by the variant fertilized with NPK + manure, followed by manure, and the highest EEG values were obtained for manure followed by the variant fertilized with NPK + manure, and then the control.

The correlation between glomalin content and soil properties revealed a significant positive correlation of TG or EEG content with the aromatic ($R = 0.453, 0.538$, and 0.516 for TG, and $R = 0.591, 0.524$, and 0.461 for EEG) and hydrophilic ($R = 0.565, 0.711$, and 0.453 for TG, and $R = 0.653, 0.659$, and 0.444 for EEG) components of SOM (Tables S2, S4, S6) at all sites.

The hypothesis that an increase in the content of glycoproteins also leads to an increase in the HI value (corresponding to the potential wettability index in a study by Balík et al., 2022) was not confirmed in our study. The results for Ivanovice show even the opposite trend, as, for example, there were significant negative correlations ($R = -0.606$ and -0.606) between the HI value and TG or EEG, respectively.

Furthermore, significant positive correlation was found between TG and C_{tot} ($R = 0.769$) and N_{tot} ($R = 0.730$) in Čáslav, as well as between EEG and C_{tot} ($R = 0.664$ and 0.744) and N_{tot} ($R = 0.745$ and 0.707) in Čáslav and Lukavec, respectively, (Balík et al., 2020; Rezáčová et al., 2021; Šarapatka et al., 2019; Wright and Upadhyaya, 1998).

3.3. Soil hydrophysical properties

All measures of soil characteristics (θ_{field} , θ_s , θ_{30} , θ_{MKK} , θ_{RVK} , and P) obtained from analyses of the undisturbed soil samples taken during the summer sampling events from soils fertilized with manure were usually higher (for ρ_d lower) than those for the control. Due to the great variability among the measured values, however, the differences between the different scenarios were, with some exceptions, not significant. Nevertheless, this suggests that farm manure increased soils' porosity and retention ability. This is in agreement with a finding by Zhang et al. (2006), who studied influence of different fertilization treatments (no fertilizer, NPK, and NPK + manure) on hydraulic properties, bulk density, porosity, SOM, and soil water content.

Correlations between these properties and C_{tot} (Tables S3, S5, S7) revealed, for example, significant relationships between C_{tot} and θ_s , θ_{30} , and/or θ_{MKK} ($R = 0.430, 0.432$, and 0.324 , respectively) for Čáslav and between C_{tot} and θ_s , θ_{30} , and/or P ($R = 0.422, 0.264$, and 0.259 , respectively) for Lukavec. It is noteworthy that even stronger correlations were found between N_{tot} and θ_s , θ_{30} , θ_{MKK} , and/or θ_{RVK} ($R = 0.372, 0.548, 0.515$, and 0.352 , respectively) for Čáslav, N_{tot} and P ($R = 0.506$) for Ivanovice, and between N_{tot} and θ_s , θ_{30} , θ_{MKK} , θ_{RVK} and/or P ($R = 0.606, 0.430, 0.355, 0.290$, and 0.588 , respectively) for Lukavec. These correlations may indicate a positive influence of organic matter and nutrients on development of the soil pores system due to a combined positive effect on the growth and activity of the root system but also similar effects on the activity of other organisms and the stability of the soil structure.

3.4. Soil structure stability

3.4.1. Influence of fertilization

The greatest stability of soil aggregates (SAS values in Fig. 2, Tables 1 and 2) was detected at the Lukavec site. This is probably due to the high soil content of Fe_{ox} (4537 mg kg^{-1}) and especially of Al_{ox} (2607 mg kg^{-1}) (values obtained in 2018 using oxalate extraction according to Buurman et al., 1996, unpublished data), which have been shown to increase aggregate stability (Pavlů et al., 2022; Rasmussen et al., 2018). The higher SAS may also be due to greater content of the aliphatic hydrophobic component of SOM, which is associated with aggregate lower wettability (i.e., also higher HI values) and thus greater protection for soil aggregates. The distribution of hydrophilic and hydrophobic groups and their mutual orientation in soil aggregates determine the ratio of water repellency and wettability of SOM (Fér et al., 2016; Mayerová et al., 2023; Pavlů et al., 2023; Thai et al., 2022). For example, Thai et al. (2022) showed that the potential wettability index, PWI (corresponding to the HI values in our study), of aggregates was larger than the PWI of ground soil. This means that aggregates contain a larger amount of hydrophobic groups stabilizing the soil structure. Similarly, Urbanek et al. (2007) suggested that more hydrophilic groups are present in the exterior of aggregates than in their interior. However, Fér et al. (2016) also documented that the influence of SOM composition of aggregate coatings on their wettability decreases with increasing soil moisture.

The lowest SAS for both soils developed on loess (i.e., Chernozem in Ivanovice and Phaeozem in Čáslav, soils of better chemical and physical quality) were mostly measured for soils fertilized with NPK + manure. Similar effect had been observed by Stehlíková et al. (2016) for the same soil in Ivanovice during the 2-year period 2013–2014. No effect and a slightly negative impact of NPK + manure on the stability of soil aggregates from Chernozem and Luvisol, respectively, were found by Madaras et al. (2024). As reported by Guo et al. (2019), mineral fertilization can have a negative effect on soil aggregation. This may be due to a decrease in pH and the accumulation of large amounts of NH_4^{+} in soils. Another possible reason is the increased decomposition of organic matter in the soil caused by the presence of N. Mostly no effect of manure fertilizer in comparison to control was detected for the Phaeozem, and even slightly negative impact was observed for the Chernozem. Our findings contrast with previously published studies (e.g., Abdalla et al., 2023; Gautam et al., 2022; Mi et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2021), where manure or a combination of manure and mineral fertilizers was found to improve soil aggregation. The reason may be that, for soils such as Chernozems and Phaeozem developed on loess, which usually contain high-quality SOM (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022), manure is not a source of organic substances that would adequately substitute the function of the released or mineralized organic matter in the soil complex. Nevertheless, manure generally increased the content of organic carbon in both cases (Tables 1 and 2). Consistent with previously published studies, the lowest SAS values were mostly measured for the control treatment in the case of soil developed on gneiss (i.e., Cambisol in Lukavec). This is likely because the natural chemical and physical quality of Cambisols is poorer than that of soils like Chernozems or Phaeozems (i.e., IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022; Nikodem et al., 2021). Therefore, the manure fertilization of this type of soil in both cases increased organic matter content and improved SAS. In addition, the possible negative effect of mineral fertilizers was not so pronounced, likely because aggregates were also stabilized by Fe and Al oxides.

The positive influence of SOM hydrophobicity on SAS discussed above was also proven by the positive correlation (Tables S2, S4, and S6) between the HI and SAS values ($R = 0.507$ and 0.328) for Čáslav and Ivanovice but not for Lukavec ($R = -0.285$). Moreover, it is usually anticipated that soil structure stability will be positively correlated with SOM content (e.g., Jaksík et al., 2015; Pavlů et al., 2021). However, the only positive correlation between the SAS and C_{tot} values (Tables S2–S7) was proven for Lukavec ($R = 0.591$) during spring sampling while negative correlations were obtained in Čáslav ($R = -0.353$) and in

Fig. 2. Effect of treatment on soil aggregate stability (SAS) at selected sites, in monitored years, with spring and summer sampling. Different letters indicate significant differences at $\alpha = 0.05$ (Tukey's HSD test). Vertical lines show 95 % confidence intervals. Results from different treatments are compared for each year.

Ivanovice ($R = -0.518$). These results support the previous consideration that SAS depends not only on the amount of organic matter in the soil but above all on its composition, which is determined by its source. The different behavior of soils in Lukavec can also be explained by: a) different climatic conditions compared to those in Čáslav and Ivanovice, b) cementing effect of the Fe and other oxides in the Cambisol, and c) no or low effect of mineral fertilizer in the case of the NPK + manure scenario for Cambisol. It should also be said that in all cases (both spring

and summer sampling events in all soil types) the SAS values were strongly and negatively correlated with both field soil water contents (i. e., w_{field} and θ_{field}). Such effect, which could mask the real function of various soil components, has also been demonstrated by (among others) Jakšík et al. (2015), Jirků et al. (2013), and Perfect et al. (1990). Perhaps for similar reasons, positive correlations were not detected between the SAS values and the total (TG) or easily extractable (EEG) glomalin contents, as was observed by (among others) Řezáčová et al. (2021) and

Fig. 3. Soil aggregate stability during spring and summer sampling, in individual years, and at individual sites (top row). Different letters indicate significant differences at significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ (Tukey's HSD test). Vertical lines show 95 % confidence intervals. Results from different seasons are compared for each year. Field volumetric soil water content in individual years during summer sampling (bottom row).

Wright and Anderson (2000). Instead, negative correlations were found at Čáslav ($R = -0.792$ for TG and $R = -0.872$ for EEG) and Ivanovice ($R = -0.646$ for TG and $R = -0.634$ for EEG). Ambiguous relationships were also observed between the SAS and N_{tot} values (Tables S2–S7). Negative correlations between SAS and N_{tot} were observed at Čáslav and Ivanovice but not at Lukavec. Similar negative relationships had been proven also by Are et al. (2018), who studied SAS with different doses of N and regardless of manure fertilization. Because aggregates from Cambisol in Lukavec were likely stabilized by Fe and Al oxides, as discussed above, the expected negative effect of N on SAS (e.g., Are et al., 2018; Guo et al., 2019) was not obvious. Finally, positive correlations were found between SAS and θ_s for Čáslav ($R = 0.396$) and Ivanovice ($R = 0.430$), and this may be associated with a better development of soil pore structure and its stability.

3.4.2. Seasonal and annual variability

Seasonal variability in the stability of soil aggregates during the years 2014–2021 was also evaluated at individual sites (Fig. 3). Differences between individual years and seasons were found. As in the study by Jirků et al. (2013), SAS was greater at the end of the growing season but depended on the amount of precipitation (Fig. S1). As stated by Hillel (2004), SAS depends on stage of root zone development, soil management, and climatic conditions. SAS is positively influenced by root growth and other biological activities and negatively influenced by intense rainfall. As shown in Fig. 3, the SAS values to some degree follow trends opposite those of the corresponding field soil water contents (θ_{field}). Similarly, Perfect et al. (1990) and Jirků et al. (2013) found seasonal (seasonal and interannual, respectively) fluctuations in SAS to be significantly and negatively related to soil water content at the time of sampling.

3.4.3. Prediction of SAS values

Because soil aggregation reflects interaction among chemical, physical, and biological soil factors (Portella et al., 2012), we aimed to analyze the data comprehensively while expressing relationships between SAS and other soil properties using multiple linear regression (Table 3). Different combinations of the variables were tested to account for relevant characteristics (found in the correlation analysis) that were not mutually correlated. A relevant variable was first chosen and then additional variables were gradually included into the multiple regression equation so that the highest possible R -values were obtained while p -values remained below 0.05. Although the resulting regression equations approximated the measured values relatively well (see R^2 and p -values in Table 3), different sets of parameters in the models for different sites indicate that it is not possible to obtain similar models for areas of different soil types. A similar conclusion had been reached by Pavlů et al. (2022), who evaluated equations for predicting aggregate stability for four localities with different soil types. That is because stability of soil structure is influenced by many and diverse soil and climatic conditions that can interact variably at different locations. Nevertheless, several variants in Table 3 point to the possibility of forecasting stability of the soil aggregate using different data that were available for the given period. As could be expected based on the previous discussion, almost all equations showed a negative relationship with field soil water content (either w_{field} for spring or θ_{field} for summer). Inclusion of soil moisture into the multiple regression models did not, however, help to explain the effect of soil properties on SAS that was opposite from what been expected, as discussed in section 3.3.1. For example, negative relationships with C_{tot} were again observed at Čáslav and Ivanovice and a positive relationship at Lukavec. As discussed above, however, this likely was due to the quality of organic matter and its function in the soil complex. In several cases, there was even a reverse effect as the original correlation, which had appeared logical, changed to just the opposite. For example, the positive correlation between the SAS and HI values at Ivanovice (Table S4) changed to a negative relationship (Table 1).

Table 3

Multiple linear regression models for predicting soil aggregate stability (SAS). Presented equations include soil organic matter components (hydrophobic aliphatic, aromatic, hydrophilic), DI – decomposition index, HI – hydrophobicity index, C_{tot} – total organic carbon (%), N_{tot} – total organic nitrogen (%), pH_{H_2O} , TG – total glomalin ($mg\ g^{-1}$), EEG – easily extracted glomalin ($mg\ g^{-1}$), w_{field} – gravimetric water content (%), ρ_d – bulk density ($g\ cm^{-3}$), θ_{field} – field soil water content (%), θ_s – saturated soil water content (%). Analyses always included all data (from all sampling years) available for each set of related values (n). R^2 is the coefficient of determination and p indicates statistical significance.

site	season	Regression equations	R^2	p	n
Čáslav	spring	SAS = 64.26*** – 6.87aromatic*** – 6.05TG***	0.78	***	24
		SAS = 158.64*** + 9.13aliphatic*** – 39.61 C_{tot} – 11.24 pH_{H_2O} ***	0.69	***	36
		SAS = 185.34*** – 10.35aromatic*** – 30.70 C_{tot} – 10.66 pH_{H_2O} **	0.61	***	36
	summer	SAS = 91.97*** – 1.74 θ_{field} *** – 11.57 C_{tot} *	0.88	***	66
		SAS = 34.78* – 1.78 θ_{field} *** – 16.56 C_{tot} ** + 42.02 ρ_d ***	0.91	***	66
		SAS = 61.57*** – 9.92 C_{tot} * – 1.38 w_{field} ***	0.88	***	36
	spring	SAS = 50.47*** – 1.57 w_{field} *** – 4.97alifatic***	0.85	***	48
		SAS = 28.91*** – 1.55 w_{field} *** + 4.41aromatic**	0.83	***	48
		SAS = 31.86*** – 1.59 w_{field} *** + 1.89hydrophilic*	0.81	***	48
	Ivanovice	SAS = 39.30*** – 1.55 w_{field} *** + 1.52DI***	0.84	***	48
		SAS = 49.72*** – 1.62 w_{field} *** – 24.30HI***	0.84	***	48
		SAS = 21.88* + 20.24 ρ_d * – 0.94 θ_{field} ***	0.34	***	78
Lukavec	summer	SAS = 8.99 – 1.11 θ_{field} *** – 8.75 C_{tot} + 1.43 θ_s *	0.63	***	78
		SAS = 63.77*** – 71.87 N_{tot} ** – 0.89 θ_{field} ***	0.48	***	66
		SAS = –26.18 – 1.70 θ_{field} *** + 1.31 θ_s ** + 35.93 ρ_d – 30.51 C_{tot} ** + 213.91 N_{tot} **	0.68	***	60
	spring	SAS = 23.87** + 24.71 C_{tot} *** – 8.64TG**	0.79	***	12
		SAS = –121.98*** – 0.77 w_{field} ** + 27.63 C_{tot} *** + 20.92 pH_{H_2O} ***	0.55	***	36
		SAS = 35.26** – 0.96 θ_{field} *** + 20.48 C_{tot} *	0.41	***	66
summer	SAS = 51.68*** – 1.07 θ_{field} *** + 44.92 C_{tot} *** – 257.98 N_{tot} *	0.46	***	66	

*, **, *** Significant at the probability level 0.05, 0.01, and 0.001, respectively.

3.5. General influence of different treatments on soil properties

Principal component analyses of different sets of parameters obtained during the spring or summer sampling events revealed a dominant influence of sampling year, which mostly masked the impact of the treatment. Analyses of the soil properties (SAS; C_{hw1} ; C_{tot} ; N_{tot} ; aliphatic, aromatic, and hydrophilic SOM components; DI; and HI) available for spring seasons in 2018, 2020 and 2021 (Figs. S3 and S4) showed that the effects of year for Čáslav and Ivanovice differed from that for Lukavec. While the analyses for Čáslav and Ivanovice showed similarity of the years 2018 and 2021, the analysis for Lukavec indicated similarity of the years 2020 and 2021 (Fig. S4). This suggests that the behavior of soils developed on the same loess substrate and affected by similar climatic conditions differs from the behavior of the Cambisol developed on gneiss and influenced by diverse climatic conditions. Inclusion of the w_{field} values into the analyses (Figs. S5 and S6) did not significantly change the observed trends.

Similarly, analyses of the soil properties (SAS, C_{tot} , N_{tot} , θ_{field} , θ_s , ρ_d , and P) obtained for summer samplings in 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, and 2020 (Figs. S7 and S8) also showed that the impact of year for Lukavec

differed considerably from those for Čáslav and Ivanovice (e.g., similar overlap of data points given by components 1 and 2 for years 2015, 2018 and 2020 for Čáslav and Ivanovice, which differ from those for Lukavec). However, the combination of other components also showed differences between these two locations. Inclusion of other available parameters (i.e., θ_{30} , θ_{MVK} , and θ_{RVK}) yielded nothing that would help to better clarify the observed trends (Figs. S9 and S10).

As mentioned above, the effect of the treatments on tested sets of properties was less evident. In the cases of spring sampling events at Ivanovice and Lukavec, the PCA plots for both fertilization treatments (Figs. S4 and S6) indicated some similarities, and both partly deviated from the control. For Čáslav, data points indicated a slight shift from control to manure and to NPK + manure. For summer sampling events (Figs. S8 and S10), almost no differences were indicated for Lukavec and only slight differences between the variants were found for the other two locations.

3.6. Influence of different treatments on agricultural crop yields

Contrary to observations related to the soil structure characteristics (e.g., aggregate stability), the highest yield (Fig. S2) was usually obtained for plots fertilized with NPK + manure. This could be expected due to the nutrients added to the soil. Nevertheless, no impact of NPK on yield was observed, for example, for winter wheat at Lukavec in 2014 or oat at Čáslav and Ivanovice in 2020. Weather effects may be the cause, as studies by Addy et al. (2020), Hlisenkovský et al. (2023), and Morgounov et al. (2014) have shown warmer weather to be positively correlated with yields. This phenomenon is due to a higher probability of seedling emergence and a longer time for plant development before winter, which improves the prospects for overwintering. Higher temperatures in May and sufficient precipitation (Fig. S1) promote the growth and development of wheat after winter and reduce the risk from spring frosts, while higher summer temperatures accelerate ripening and reduce the risk of root and stem damage. Another reason for the comparable yield at Lukavec in 2014 may be the improving effect of the pre-crop (red clover in 2013). Hlisenkovský et al. (2023) had observed this in their study and stated that alfalfa as a pre-crop was able to provide wheat with sufficient N such that unfertilized control treatments produced grain yield (6.8 t ha^{-1}) comparable to those under fertilization treatments. Regarding the comparison of control and variants fertilized with manure, in many cases yield for the fertilized variant was slightly higher than that for the control. Nevertheless, those differences were in many cases not significant. The largest differences between yields were found for potatoes grown during 2019 at Čáslav and Ivanovice, which have high-quality, usually more-fertile soils. The highest yields were again recorded for the plots fertilized with NPK and manure, followed by those for plots fertilized with manure and the control. In summary, from the viewpoint of plant production, the NPK + manure variants are the best, which is in line with previous findings (e.g., Chen et al., 2018; Hlisenkovský et al., 2014; Macholdt et al., 2019). However, this benefit comes at the expense of soil structure quality, as illustrated by the aggravated soil aggregates stability in the high-quality soils at Čáslav and Ivanovice. As our results have shown, manure is not a source of sufficient-quality organic matter that would help fundamentally to improve soil structure in these NPK-fertilized (and also non-NPK-fertilized) soils. Therefore, it would probably be appropriate to combine NPK fertilization with another type of organic fertilizer (e.g., Chen et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2023; Zhu et al., 2021).

4. Conclusion

This study provided a comprehensive analysis as to the long-term effect of farmyard manure and mineral fertilizers on the stability of soil aggregates in three different soils. Because soil structure is affected by current climatic conditions and the crops grown each year, the aggregate stability was studied over an 8-year period. A synthesis of all

available soil characteristics was used to identify the effects of different soil properties on the stability of aggregates in individual soils. In general, manure fertilization increased SAS only in the Cambisol developed on gneiss but had no effect in the other two, better-quality soils, Chernozem and Phaeozem (both developed on loess). This contradicts the original hypothesis. In addition, aggregate stability was reduced in these two soils when they were simultaneously fertilized with mineral fertilizer. Soils fertilized with manure tended to contain more organic carbon and showed slightly higher values for hydro-physical parameters. The regression analyses revealed a greater dependence of SAS on the field (sampling) soil water content than on the properties controlling soil aggregations (e.g., total soil organic carbon). For the Phaeozem and the Chernozem, a positive influence of hydrophobic organic matter components on aggregate stability was demonstrated. On the contrary, no positive effect of glomalin was proven. PCA analyses proved year to have a dominant impact, but influence of different treatments was also evident.

Our results show that although farmyard manure can improve some chemical and structural properties in all three soils, it may not – as is generally assumed – increase the stability of soil aggregates in high-quality soils (such as Chernozems). The results also show a positive effect of NPK fertilization on increasing yield at all locations. Its long-term use can have a negative effect on soil quality, however, so it is necessary to look for more sustainable management methods. The use of manure to improve soil structure can be recommended for Cambisols. In the cases of the other two soils, it would be appropriate to test other sources of organic fertilizers that can provide better-quality soil organic components. These might improve the stability of soil aggregates and thus contribute to reducing the negative effect of mineral fertilizers.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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